

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**NOCTURNAL ENURESIS IN CHILDREN AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL
PROBLEM IN SAUDI ARABIA: SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**

Rawan Wadi A Alanazi¹, Sawsan Hassan Abdullah Hashim², Rawan Hamdan Salem Alenazy¹, Raghad Aladham Alanazi¹, Razan Mohammed G Aldahmashi¹, Aml Batah H Alenezi¹, Hayat Faisal S Alnathir¹, Mona Theyab Alanazi¹, Maram Mohammed M Alanazi¹, Itizaz Hatim R Alanazi¹, Taif Shayish N Alanazi¹

¹ Faculty of Medicine, Northern Border University, KSA

² Associate Prof. of Pediatrics, Faculty of Medicine, Northern Border University, KSA.

Article Received: December 2019 Accepted: January 2020 Published: February 2020

Abstract:

Background: the etiology of nocturnal enuresis include genetic and familial factors, psychological factors, bladder diseases, hormonal deregulations, as well as sleep disorders. **Objectives:** To investigate the prevalence of Nocturnal enuresis and its associated psychological problems specially in Saudi Arabia and ideal the management that could be used in this condition in children aged 6-12 years. **Methods:** it was a review article. Data Collected During The Period From 1– 31 October, 2019. Medline, PubMed and EBSCO database searches was performed for the publications about the prevalence of Nocturnal enuresis and its associated psychological problems specially in Saudi Arabia. The keywords search headings included "Nocturnal enuresis, Nocturnal enuresis associated psychological problems, Saudi Arabia", and a combination of these was used. **Results:** Concerning the previous studies, our study documented that, child anxiety and low positive affectivity, maternal history of anxiety, low authoritative parenting parent, generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, school phobia, social anxiety, separation anxiety, history of primary nocturnal enuresis in parent's family, internalizing disorders (such as depressive and anxiety disorders), which are less common than externalizing ones (such as ADHD), subclinical emotional and behavioral symptoms and body mass index had a significant relation with nocturnal enuresis. **Conclusion:** Our study concluded that, child anxiety and low positive affectivity, maternal history of anxiety, low authoritative parenting parent, generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, school phobia, social anxiety, separation anxiety, history of primary nocturnal enuresis in parent's family, internalizing disorders had a significant relation with nocturnal enuresis.

Key words: Nocturnal Enuresis, children, associated, psychological problems, Saudi Arabia

Corresponding author:

Rawan Wadi A Alanazi,

Faculty of Medicine, Northern Border University, KSA

QR code

Please cite this article in press Rawan Wadi A Alanazi et al., *Nocturnal Enuresis In Children As A Psychological Problem In Saudi Arabia: Review Article.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(02).

INTRODUCTION:

Nocturnal enuresis, also referred to as nighttime incontinence, is a relatively common disorder among children. It is defined as the repeated, spontaneous passage of urine during sleep beyond the age of anticipated full nocturnal bladder control, which is generally accepted to be five years of age. ^[1] It is three times more common than daytime incontinence and it affects 6.7% of younger children and 2.8% of older children. ^[2] Meanwhile, the incidence among adolescents aged 15-18 is 1%. ^[3] It is three times more common among young boys than young girls. ^[4] Several theories have been proposed for the etiology of nocturnal enuresis. These include genetic and familial factors, psychologic factors, bladder diseases, hormonal dysregulation, as well as sleep disorders. ^[5] Genetic predisposition seems to be the most supported associated variable. The review of **Norgaard *et al.*** showed that when the two parents of the child were enuretic as children, the risk of their offspring having nocturnal enuresis was as high as 77%. ^[6]

Nocturnal enuresis is often troubling for children and their families, which puts them in stressful situations. Although, studies examining primary enuresis and its association with psychologic comorbidities are limited, it has been shown that nocturnal enuresis is associated with externalizing problem behaviors, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). ^[7, 8] The study of Biederman *et al.* found that the association between ADHD and nocturnal enuresis is of 30% greater chance than non-enuretic adolescents. ^[9] On the other hand, studies found that enuresis is associated with lower self-esteem and greater levels of internalizing behaviors, which were attributed to distress, shame and familiar intolerance of the condition. ^[10, 11]

Rationale:

Nocturnal enuresis whether primary or secondary is very troubling for children and their families, it is one of the stressful situations, up to our knowledge, studies examining its psychological comorbidities in Saudi Arabia are limited,

Study Objectives:

To investigate the prevalence of Nocturnal enuresis and its associated psychological problems specially in Saudi Arabia and ideal the management that could be used in this condition in children aged 6-12 years.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

Study Design: Review article.

Study duration: Data Collected During The Period From 1– 31 October, 2019.

Data collection: Medline, PubMed and EBSCO database searches was performed for the publications about the prevalence of Nocturnal enuresis and its associated psychological problems specially in Saudi Arabia, as they are high-quality sources. published in English around the world. The keywords search headings included “Nocturnal enuresis, Nocturnal enuresis associated psychological problems, Saudi Arabia”, and a combination of these was used. Restriction to the last 10 years, country restriction on Saudi Arabia, and English language due to unavailable resources for translation were used. References list of each included study will be searched for further supportive data.

Statistical analysis:

No software has been utilized to analyse the data. The data was extracted based on specific form that contain (Title of the publication, author’s name, objective and results). These data were reviewed by the group members to determine its initial findings. Double revision of each member was applied to ensure the validity and minimize the mistakes.

RESULTS:

Concerning the previous studies, our study documented that, child anxiety and low positive affectivity, maternal history of anxiety, low authoritative parenting parent, generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, school phobia, social anxiety, separation anxiety, history of primary nocturnal enuresis in parent’s family, internalizing disorders (such as depressive and anxiety disorders), which are less common than externalizing ones (such as ADHD), subclinical emotional and behavioural symptoms and body mass index had a significant relation with nocturnal enuresis.

Table (1): Author's name, objective and results of the studies used in our article

Main author's name	Study Objective	Result	Ref.
Salehi B et al.	To study generalized anxiety disorder as one of the possible causes of primary nocturnal enuresis.	Frequency of generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, school phobia, social anxiety, separation anxiety, history of anxiety in mother, history of primary nocturnal enuresis in parent's family and body mass index had a significant relation with nocturnal enuresis ($P = 0.005$).	12
Joinson C et al.	To investigate the psychological problems associated with bedwetting and combined (day and night) wetting in children aged around 7½ years.	The study found a higher rate of parent-reported psychological problems in children with bedwetting and combined wetting compared with those with no wetting problems. Children with combined wetting were particularly at risk for externalizing problems.	13
Kessel EM et al.	Exploring its antecedents and implications is surprisingly limited, perhaps because the condition typically remits in middle childhood.	Significant age 3 predictors of developing primary enuresis at age 9 included child anxiety and low positive affectivity, maternal history of anxiety, and low authoritative parenting. In addition, poorer global functioning and more depressive and anxiety symptoms at age 3 predicted a greater likelihood of persistence through age 9. By age 9, 77% of children who had received a diagnosis of primary enuresis were in remission and continent. However, children who had remitted exhibited a higher rate of ADHD and greater ADHD and depressive symptoms at age 9 compared to children with no lifetime history of enuresis.	14
	To examine the relationships between nocturnal enuresis in childhood and measures of behavioral adjustment in adolescence using data collected during the course of a 15-year longitudinal study of a birth cohort of New Zealand children.	The analysis showed that children who were bed-wetting after the age of 10 years as a result of either primary or secondary enuresis had increased rates of behavioral problems up to the age of 15 years with these children having mean behavior scores that were between .30 to .65 standard deviations higher than children who ceased bed-wetting before the age of 5 years. Regression analysis indicated that these associations were largely spurious and arose because the age of cessation of bedwetting was correlated with a series of factors (gender, social maturity, childhood IQ, family social background, family stress, and parental conflict) that were also associated with increased rates of adolescent behavior problems. However, even after adjusting for these factors, children who were bed-wetting after the age of 10 years showed slight increases in rates of conduct problems and attention deficit behaviors up to the age of 13 years and increases rates of anxiety/withdrawal up to the age of 15 years.	15
Ergänzte et al.	Discuss psychological and psychiatric aspects of nocturnal enuresis and functional urinary incontinence	Children with secondary nocturnal enuresis and voiding postponement carry the highest risk for a mental disorder and those with urge incontinence and primary monosymptomatic nocturnal enuresis the lowest. Internalizing disorders (such as depressive and anxiety disorders) are less common than externalizing ones (such as ADHD). In addition, subclinical emotional and behavioral symptoms are common. These will often recede upon attaining dryness and self-esteem can increase. General screening for psychological symptoms and disturbances is recommended.	16
Grzeda MT et al.	To examine whether daytime wetting and bedwetting urinary	Children with delayed development of bladder control and persistent wetting have increased psychosocial problems in adolescence. Adolescents with UI reported a range of	17

	incontinence (UI) in childhood and adolescence are associated with psychosocial problems in adolescence.	psychosocial problems and clinicians should be aware that they might require support from psychological services.	
Aljefri et al.	to determine the prevalence of NE and its relationship with personal and family characteristics.	The overall prevalence of NE was 28.6%, with a predominance of girls, and the prevalence decreased with increasing age (P 0.002) and a higher number of siblings (P = 0.01).	18
Alshahrani et al.	to estimate the prevalence of NE among children and to identify the characteristics of children who has NE. The third aim is to identify the consultation pattern to solve this problem.	Out of 65 families that have children with NE, 38.7% was the frequency of bedwetting every night; 22.6% of the children were stressed as a result of new child birth; 14% of the families did not feel a family load of having children with NE; 29% of the families did not try to treat their children because of their improvement with time; and 12% of the families that tried to treat their children used fluid restriction and waked their children up frequently at night.	19
Mohammad Alnajjar	To estimate the prevalence of nocturnal enuresis and determine its associated factors among primary school children in Al-Eskan region, Makkah Al-Mokarramah, 2013.	Out of 178 questionnaires distributed to school children, 152 questionnaires were returned completed giving a response rate of 85.4%. Their age ranged between 6 and 12 years with a mean of 9.5 and standard deviation of 1.8 years. The prevalence of nocturnal enuresis among primary school children was 8.6%. Among enuretic primary schoolchildren, nocturnal enuresis was considered primary in 84.6% while it was considered secondary in 15.4% of them. Nocturnal enuresis was more frequent among children at the age of 8 years, those who live with either father or mother, with history of parental consanguinity, low-income families, low educated fathers, living in smaller number of rooms, those having recurrent UTI, stool incontinence, habit of eating chocolate or fast foods at dinner, psychological trouble (changing school or home, loosing of admirable person, parental separation and acute family problem) and those having history of nocturnal enuresis among siblings. Among children with a history of bedwetting, only parents of two children (4.1%) tried herbal and traditional medicine and another 2 parents (4.1%) reported medical consultation. No treatment was prescribed for any cases.	20
Saad S. Al-Zahrani	to determine the frequency and types of treatment of enuresis among primary school children in Taif city.	The frequency of nocturnal enuresis was 7.81 %. There were no significant between boys (7.33%) and girls (8.42%). Treatment methods used were: enuresis alarm, water restriction, medication, and awaking for voiding in 56.9%, 14.7%, 5.7% and 5.7% of cases respectively.	21

DISCUSSION:

Psychological factors have been widely accepted as playing a major role in the pathogenesis of nocturnal enuresis [22]. Nocturnal enuresis is the term used by the International Children's Continence Society to describe bedwetting in children aged 5 years or older after ruling out organic causes. The aetiology of bedwetting is believed to be multifactorial, involving a complex interrelationship of biological, developmental, genetic, psychosocial and environmental factors [23].

NE is generally associated with fragmented sleep, lower proportions of motionless sleep, and higher

nighttime awakening [24]. NE in school-age children is associated with emotional distress, behaviour problems and lower quality of life in cross-sectional studies and poor self-image in a small case-control study. It is believed that the association between psychosocial problems and incontinence is bidirectional [25, 26].

The association between difficult temperament/psychological problems and bedwetting could be due to a common underlying neurobiological deficit. Temperament has been defined as constitutional differences in reactivity

(biological arousability) and self-regulation, and is believed to have a neurobiological basis [27]. Schober (2004) [28] conducted a study of 110 children assessed attachment psychopathology on the AAQ angry distress scale and the care givers dissociation scores. The study showed children with nocturnal enuresis had significantly higher scores on the AAQ angry distress scale, showing greater psychopathology, compared to children without nocturnal enuresis. There was no statistically significant difference in the scores between females and males, or between those who were breast fed and those who were not.

Theunis (2002) [29] reported that Children with nocturnal enuresis were reported to have significantly lower global self-esteem ($p < 0.01$) and physical appearance ($p < 0.05$) than children without nocturnal enuresis. There was a trend to a lower perceived competence in enuretic children concerning their scholastic skills and social acceptance, but it was not significant. Regarding social acceptance ($p < 0.05$), physical appearance ($p < 0.05$) and global self-esteem ($p < 0.05$), the 10–12 year old enuretic children had the lower perceived competence and the 10–12 years old non-enuretic children had the highest perceived competence.

Wolfe-Christensen et al. conducted a survey on “psychosocial problems in children referred to urology clinics” and reported that in total 15.2% of children had serious psychosocial and social problems and greater risk of mental problems and with increasing mental-social problems the severity of urology disease also increased [30].

Buluğ reported the frequencies of accompanying psychiatric diagnoses in primary and secondary nocturnal enuresis. The most common accompanying diagnosis in children and adolescents diagnosed with enuresis was found to be Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (primary: 29.79%; secondary: 24.32%). In the children who had secondary enuresis, depression was found with a rate of 19.5 %, specific phobia was found with a rate of 17.02%, social phobia was found with a rate of 14.89%, separation anxiety was found with a rate of 12.76% and oppositional defiant disorder was found with a rate of 12.76% [31].

Behavioral methods have proven to be quite successful in improving adherence and include many simple techniques the provider can easily introduce into practice, for example the use of (social) rewards to increase motivation. Use creative and original methods that do concern the child. Let patients indicate in a diary whether they

were adherent with treatment guidelines. The diary functions as a (self)-controlling mechanism to increase adherence [32, 33].

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that, child anxiety and low positive affectivity, maternal history of anxiety, low authoritative parenting parent, generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, school phobia, social anxiety, separation anxiety, history of primary nocturnal enuresis in parent’s family, internalizing disorders (such as depressive and anxiety disorders), which are less common than externalizing ones (such as ADHD), subclinical emotional and behavioral symptoms and body mass index had a significant relation with nocturnal enuresis.

Conflict of interest: the authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

Funding institutions: there is no funding institution.

REFERENCES:

1. Kiddoo DA. Nocturnal enuresis. *CMAJ*. 2012;184(8):908-911.
2. Stein MA, Mendelsohn J, Obermeyer WH et al. Sleep and behavior problems in school-aged children. *Pediatrics*. 2001;107(4):E60.
3. Sadock BJ, Sadock VA. Kaplan & Sadock’s comprehensive textbook of psychiatry, 9th ed. New York: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. 2009;pp:3560-79.
4. Miller K. Concomitant nonpharmacologic therapy in the treatment of primary nocturnal enuresis. *Clin Pediatr (Phila)*. 1993;Spec No:32-37.
5. Thiedke CC. Nocturnal enuresis. *Am Fam Physician*. 2003;67:1499-506.
6. Norgaard JP, Djurhuus JC, Watanabe H et al. Experience and current status of research into the pathophysiology of nocturnal enuresis. *Br J Urol*. 1997;79:825-35.
7. Equit M, Klein MEA, von Gontard A. Elimination disorder and anxious-depressed symptoms in preschool children: a population-based study. *Eur Child Adolesc Psy*. 2013;23(6):417-423.
8. Van Hoecke E, Baeyens D, Vande Walle J et al. Socioeconomic status as a common factor underlying the association between enuresis and psychopathology. *J Dev Behav Pediatr*. 2003;24(2):109-114.
9. Biederman J, Santangelo SL, Faraone SV et al. Clinical correlates of enuresis in ADHD and non ADHD children. *J Child Psychol Psychiatry*. 1995;36(5):865-877.
10. Hägglöf B, Andrén O, Bergström E et al. Self-esteem before and after treatment in children

- with nocturnal enuresis and urinary incontinence. *Scand J Urol Nephrol Suppl.* 1997;183:79-82.
11. Butler RJ. Annotation: night wetting in children: psychological aspects. *J Child Psychol Psychiatry.* 1998;39(4):453-463.
 12. Salehi B, Yousefichaijan P, Rafeei M, Mostajeran M. The Relationship Between Child Anxiety Related Disorders and Primary Nocturnal Enuresis. *Iran J Psychiatry Behav Sci.* 2016;10(2):e4462. Published 2016 May 17. doi:10.17795/ijpbs-4462
 13. Carol Joinson, Jon Heron, Alan Emond, Richard Butler, Psychological Problems in Children with Bedwetting and Combined (day and night) Wetting: A UK Population-Based Study, *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, Volume 32, Issue 5, June 2007, Pages 605–616, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsl039>
 14. Kessel EM, Allmann AE, Goldstein BL, et al. Predictors and Outcomes of Childhood Primary Enuresis. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry.* 2017;56(3):250–257. doi:10.1016/j.jaac.2016.12.007
 15. David M. Fergusson, L. John Horwood. Nocturnal Enuresis and Behavioral Problems in Adolescence: A 15-Year Longitudinal Study. *Pediatrics* Nov 1994, 94 (5) 662-668;
 16. Ergänzte und überarbeitete Version der Arbeit: von Gontard A (2003) Psychologisch-psychiatrische Aspekte der Enuresis nocturna. *Monatsschr Kinderheilkd* 151: 945–951
 17. Grzeda MT, Heron J, von Gontard A, Joinson C. Effects of urinary incontinence on psychosocial outcomes in adolescence. *Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry.* 2017;26(6):649–658. doi:10.1007/s00787-016-0928-0
 18. Aljefri HM, Basurreh OA, Yunus F, Bawazir AA. Nocturnal Enuresis among Primary School Children. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl* 2013;24(6):1233-1241.
 19. Alshahrani A, Selim M, and Abbas M. Prevalence of nocturnal enuresis among children in Primary Health Care Centers of Family and Community Medicine, PSMCM, Riyadh City, KSA. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2018 Sep-Oct; 7(5): 937–941.
 20. Mohammad Alnajjar. Prevalence and Risk Factors Associated with Nocturnal Enuresis Among Primary School Children in Al-Eskan Region, Makkah Al-Mokarramah. *Int J Med Res Prof.* 2017 Nov; 3(6): 153-61.
 21. Saad S. Al-Zahrani. Nocturnal enuresis and its treatment among primary-school children in Taif, KSA. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2014 Feb;2(1):91-94.
 22. J. Vande Walle, S. Rittig, S. Bauer, P. Eggert, D. Marschall-Kehrel, S. Tekgul. Practical consensus guidelines for the management of enuresis. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2012;171:971-983
 23. Austin PF, Bauer S, Bower W, Chase J, Franco I, Hoebeke P, Rittig S, Vande Walle J, von Gontard A, Wright A, Yang A, Nevéus T. The standardization of terminology of bladder function in children and adolescents: update report from the Standardization Committee of the International Children's Continence Society (ICCS) *J Urol.* 2014;191:1863–1865. doi: 10.1016/j.juro.2014.01.110.
 24. Cohen-Zrubavel V, Kushnir B, Kushnir J, et al. : Sleep and sleepiness in children with nocturnal enuresis. *Sleep.* 2011;34(2):191–4. 10.1093/sleep/34.2.191
 25. Thibodeau BA, Metcalfe P, Koop P, Moore K. Urinary incontinence and quality of life in children. *J Pediatr Urol.* 2013;9(1):78–83. doi: 10.1016/j.jpuro.2011.12.005.
 26. Theunis M, Van Hoecke E, Paesbrugge S, Hoebeke P, Vande Walle J. Self-image and performance in children with nocturnal enuresis. *Eur Urol.* 2002;41(6):660–667. doi: 10.1016/S0302-2838(02)00127-6.
 27. Rothbart MK, Bates JE (2006) Temperament. In: Damon W, Lerner R, Eisenberg N (eds) *Handbook of child psychology. Social, emotional, and personality development*, vol 3, 6th edn. Wiley, New York, pp 99–166
 28. Schober JM, Lipman R, Haltigan JD, Kuhn PJ. The impact of monosymptomatic nocturnal enuresis on attachment parameters. *Scand J Urol Nephrol.* 2004;38(1):47–52.
 29. Theunis M, Van Hoecke E, Paesbrugge S, Hoebeke P, Vande Walle J. Self-image and performance in children with nocturnal enuresis. *Eur Urol.* 2002;41(6):660–667.
 30. Wolfe-Christensen C, Veenstra AL, Kovacevic L, Elder JS, Lakshmanan Y. Psychosocial difficulties in children referred to pediatric urology: a closer look. *Urology.* 2012;80(4):907–12. doi: 10.1016/j.urology.2012.04.077.
 31. Buluğ U. “Primer ve sekonder enürezis noktornada eşlik eden psikiyatrik tanı sıklıklarının belirlenmesi ve karşılaştırılması. 2009. pp. S51–58. Yayınlanmamış tıpta uzmanlık tezi.
 32. C. Van Herzeele, I. Alova, J. Evans, P. Eggert, H. Lottmann, J.P. Norgaard, et al. Poor compliance with primary nocturnal enuresis therapy may contribute to insufficient desmopressin response. *J Urol.* 2009;182:2045-2049
 33. B. Staples, T. Bravender. Drug compliance in adolescents: assessing and managing modifiable risk factors. *Paediatr Drugs.* 2002;4:503-513